

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

MANAGING PERIOPERATIVE GLUCOSE OF DIABETIC PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Perioperative glucose management is an essential component in the care of diabetic patients receiving surgery. Failure to assess and treat hyperglycemia in the perioperative setting leads to improper management of BG, increasing the risk of poor patient outcomes and increased costs from a prolonged length of stay. This project focused on understanding the barriers to glycemic control at the study site. **METHODS:** This QI project used a barriers survey as the primary tool for the paper. The sample population was the one hundred anesthesia providers at the selected Southern California hospital. The goal was to achieve at least a 20% response rate from the survey. Thematic analysis using NVivo was utilized to showcase the results further. **INTERVENTION:** Using a Qualtrics survey, anesthesia providers were asked to share their perceived barriers to glycemic control. Twenty-five out of the one hundred anesthesia providers completed the survey. Development of a CDS alert “pop-up” was also initiated. **RESULTS:** It was found that the two main barriers were access to supplies and personnel related. Providers also deemed the incorporation of an alert-based tool within the EMR as presumably useful. **CONCLUSION:** It can be concluded that access to supplies, continued education, and implementation of an alert-based tool can help increase the proper management of hyperglycemia in the perioperative period and help decrease adverse events from occurring in the postoperative period.

Keywords: Hyperglycemia, perioperative management, barriers, alert-based tools, postoperative outcomes, education, Emory protocol

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Background

Over 310 million surgeries are performed annually worldwide, and 40 to 50 million surgeries occur in the United States (Dobson, 2020). About 25% of diabetes mellitus (DM) patients require surgery over their lifetime, and the mortality rates in this population are up to five times greater than nondiabetic patients (Loh-Trivedi & Croley, 2021). With over 37 million diagnoses in the United States, DM is the most prevalent endocrine condition in surgical patients (Schwartz et al., 2017; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2021). Increased complications have economic consequences, including decreased productivity and earning potential, straining national economies (Nazir et al., 2018). The projected cost of DM in the United States in 2012 was \$245 billion, of which \$176 billion went toward direct expenses and \$69 billion toward lost productivity. Furthermore, the global economic toll of DM in 2015 was \$1.31 trillion, with indirect costs making up approximately 35% of financial losses (Nazir et al., 2018).

Millar et al. (2019) found that blood glucose (BG) monitoring in the perioperative periods was underutilized. If the healthcare provider does not maintain adequate glycemic control, it will impair the patients' physiological processes during recovery, leading to increased infections and complications in the postoperative period (Loh-Trivedi & Croley, 2021). This project paper discussed the background and significance of perioperative glucose management. It contained a thorough literature review, a supporting framework, and a method and evaluation plan to address barriers and improve glycemic control.

DM is an endocrine disorder that primarily affects glucose metabolism. In people afflicted with DM, there is either insufficient insulin secretion or insulin sensitivity in target tissues (Butterworth et al., 2018). The traditional method of diagnosing DM is performed via

serum glucose measurements. DM is diagnosed with either a fasting BG level greater than 126 mg/dL or a random BG level greater than 200 mg/dL; in both conditions, associated symptoms of polyuria, polydipsia, and polyphagia should also be noted. The diagnostic criteria for DM were revised in 2009 to include a hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) above 6.5% (Butterworth et al., 2018; Schwartz et al., 2017).

For this quality improvement (QI) project, the terms hypo-, normo-, and hyperglycemia were based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA) definitions. Hypoglycemia is defined as a BG value of less than 70 mg/dL, normoglycemia (or euglycemia) is between 70 and 130 mg/dL, and hyperglycemia is a level above 180 mg/dL (ADA Professional Practice Committee, 2022).

Due to the clinical nature of the disease, it is imperative for patients diagnosed with DM to be diligent in performing routine BG checks (Schwartz et al., 2017). DM is regarded as one of the leading causes of new-onset organ disease and mortality in most countries, with the risk of intraabdominal, breast, urinogenital, and colorectal malignancies higher among those diagnosed with DM (Karlet, 2017). Chronic hyperglycemia results in impairment and end-organ failure in many different body organs, including the heart, blood vessels, kidneys, eyes, and nerves, leading to cardiovascular diseases, chronic renal disease, progressive blindness, and non-traumatic limb loss later in life (Karlet, 2017; Schwartz et al., 2017).

The sequelae of long-standing DM predispose patients to complications that may necessitate surgical intervention. Frequently performed procedures include cataract removal, renal transplantation, wound and ulcer debridement, coronary artery bypass grafting, vascular repair, and limb amputation (Karlet, 2017; Nazir et al., 2018). Moreover, compared to nondiabetics of similar age, surgical patients with DM had more significant perioperative

morbidity and mortality rates (Schwartz et al., 2017). Adverse complications related to suboptimal glucose management—especially during the intraoperative period—are associated with poor postoperative outcomes, including delayed wound healing and dehiscence, hypothermia, infection, sepsis, delayed emergence from anesthesia, residual neuromuscular blockade, and even death (Karlet, 2017; Schwartz et al., 2017). Due to these outcomes, patients with DM undergoing surgical procedures demand optimal perioperative glycemic management. The length and type of procedure and the degree of a patient’s home self-management are all considered when controlling a patient’s glucose during surgery (Karlet, 2017).

In the operating room, glucose management is principally the responsibility of the anesthesia provider. For surgeries lasting beyond two hours, BG checks are performed every two hours, testing whole blood using a glucometer at the point of care (Dogra & Jialal, 2022; Karlet, 2017). However, the gold standard for measuring BG is analyzing and verifying arterial blood by a central laboratory (Inoue et al., 2013). Additionally, hourly instead of 2-hour BG checks are recommended for lengthy surgical procedures or any major surgery, especially for elderly patients with DM (Dogra & Jialal, 2022; Karlet, 2017). A correction dose of short-acting subcutaneous insulin or a carefully titrated intravenous insulin infusion are intraoperative regimens utilized for glycemic management (Butterworth et al., 2018; Dogra & Jialal, 2022). While there is a current debate on the optimal BG range during surgery, the overarching goal of perioperative glucose management is avoiding hypoglycemia and reducing metabolic disturbances brought on by hyperglycemia (Butterworth et al., 2018; Schwartz et al., 2017). The most recent 2019 ADA Guidelines suggest starting treatment when BG levels reach 180 mg/dL and maintaining a perioperative BG range between 80-180 mg/dL (Chen & Duggan, 2019).

The anesthetized patient undergoing surgery frequently experiences stress-induced hyperglycemia (Knaak et al., 2019). Perioperative hyperglycemia is observed in 30% to 40% of surgical patients, of which two-thirds are diabetic. There's a significant rise in the incidence of perioperative hyperglycemia among nondiabetic patients, ranging from 13% to 67% (Ding et al., 2017). Ineffective perioperative glycemic control is related to poor outcomes in diabetic and nondiabetic patients. Nair et al. (2019) found that poor management of glucose levels and large glycemic variability were associated with extended hospital stays and postoperative complications in nondiabetic patients. For diabetic patients, higher glycemic variability was associated with higher risk of mortality and complications (Nair et al., 2019). Knaak et al. (2019) investigated the risk factors of abnormal BG levels in elderly surgical patients. They found that the duration of surgery and a DM diagnosis were independent risk factors associated with adverse surgical outcomes such as postoperative delirium, acute kidney injury, and impaired cognition (Knaak et al., 2019).

Due to the risks of complications, quality anesthesia care requires conscientious intraoperative BG monitoring, even in the short term. Suboptimal intraoperative glycemic management leads to considerable morbidity and mortality and can lead to an economic burden (Nair et al., 2019; Dogra & Jialal, 2022). Two meta-analyses have identified that consistently elevated serum glucose levels are an independent risk factor for postoperative surgical site infections (SSIs) in patients undergoing liver transplant, orthopedic, breast, spine, or intraabdominal surgeries (Oliveira et al., 2020; de Vries et al., 2017). Prolonged hospitalization directly correlates with increased costs, with hyperglycemic postoperative patients incurring significantly higher hospitalization expenses (\$79,545 for DM and \$72,675 for non-DM) compared to \$20,273 for those with euglycemia. Furthermore, readmission rates within 30 days

were notably higher for hyperglycemic patients (18.8% for DM and 17.2% for non-DM) versus 9.3% for euglycemic patients (Buehler et al., 2015).

Problem Statement and Significance

Failure to use a standardized protocol contributes to improper management of BG control, risking poor patient outcomes and increased costs from a prolonged length of stay (Cannon et al., 2018; Nair et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2020). Nair et al. (2019) and Shah et al. (2020) researched how uncontrolled hyperglycemia during cardiac and elective surgery is linked to surgical site infections, sepsis, compromised cardiopulmonary function, and considerable morbidity and mortality. Patients with uncontrolled hyperglycemia had a 38.1% increased rate of 30-day morbidity and mortality compared to 30% in patients with blood sugar levels less than 180 mg/dL (Shah et al., 2020). Nair et al. (2019) found that both diabetic patients and nondiabetic patients had statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increases in length of stay with poorly controlled BG levels. Cannon et al. (2018) also found readmission costs due to poor glycaemic management were about \$77,000 for each patient (Cannon et al., 2018). The key to reducing costs and prolonged hospital visits was using an established glycaemic protocol and avoiding hypoglycemia (Cannon et al., 2018; Nair et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2020). Current evidence also addressed several barriers to glycaemic control and protocol compliance, such as the risk of hypoglycemia, lack of protocol awareness, and lack of resources (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2021; Chui et al., 2019; Correa et al., 2020; Eerdeken et al., 2020; Haque et al., 2021; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017; Pérez et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020).

The risk of perioperative hyperglycemia and its associated problems further comes down to increased costs and adverse patient outcomes (Cannon et al., 2018; Nair et al., 2019; Shah et

al., 2020). These adverse outcomes emphasize why the barriers highlighted above need to be addressed. As mentioned, the selected hospital system for this project did not employ a standardized glycemic management protocol, which led to the initiation of this project. Researchers from the Emory University School of Medicine developed an outline for the perioperative management of patients with diabetes and hyperglycemia due to surgical stress (Duggan et al., 2017). This protocol has guidelines for testing and insulin dosing specifying when to hold or administer insulin and how much to administer if needed (Duggan et al., 2017). There are also defined parameters establishing norms for hyperglycemia, hypoglycemia, and euglycemia. Utilizing this protocol as a framework and the ADA (2018) recommendation can help establish a proper standard of care in the targeted hospital.

Alcaraz et al. (2020) initiated a QI project to identify gaps in care for diabetic patients undergoing surgery. Their evaluation of 100 perioperative records from several large urban hospitals in Southern California showed that only three surgical patients had their BG measured intraoperatively (Alcaraz et al., 2020). These results highlighted the hospital practice discrepancy with current guidelines supported by research literature and major associations, including the ADA (2018) and the Joslin Diabetes Center (2019). Putman and Stitt (2022) then focused on selecting an appropriate protocol for glycemic management and finding strategies to disseminate the information to anesthesia providers at the selected project site. They adopted a protocol from the Emory School of Medicine, implemented evidenced-based education on the algorithm, and conducted pre- and post-tests to assess the knowledge of the educated providers (Putman & Stitt, 2022). A subsequent group of DNP students continued the project by performing chart audits to determine provider compliance with the perioperative BG protocol and the effect on patients' BG levels (Africano et al., 2022). Their data revealed that provider compliance with

intraoperative BG checks improved from 14% to 39% ($p = <0.001$); however, BG checks were only performed every two hours in 20% of these patients (Africano et al., 2022). These findings show there are still issues and other barriers to protocol adherence.

Purpose Statement

This project aimed to increase adherence to an intraoperative glucose management protocol among anesthesia providers and nurses in a community Health Maintenance Organization Southern California hospital. It was a continuation of previous projects that performed chart audits to identify gaps in care and introduce a selected glucose management protocol to improve care. This project identified barriers to intraoperative glycemic management, proposed evidence-based solutions, and addressed such barriers to improve patient care.

Supporting Framework

Development in science and technology has resulted in significant improvements in healthcare. Although these advancements have increased our capacity to deliver positive patient outcomes, the healthcare system has had trouble applying new information to daily practice (Cullen et al., 2022). For example, in a Southern California hospital, which was the primary setting of this QI project, perioperative glycemic management should follow evidence-based practice (EBP) guidelines. However, it was determined that anesthesia providers infrequently monitor intraoperative BG in diabetic patients (Alcaraz et al., 2020). Two factors may contribute to this observed practice gap: (1) a lack of education or awareness regarding currently existing protocols, or (2) the existence of intrinsic facility and clinician barriers (Putman & Stitt, 2022; Africano et al., 2022). In addition to suboptimal patient outcomes, preventable complications stemming from the lack of intraoperative BG monitoring and management may reduce Center of Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) reimbursement rates or require hospitals to provide care

uncompensated by CMS (Duggan et al., 2017). Thus, it was imperative that providers critically appraise up-to-date research and integrate evidence into their practice in addition to their clinical expertise.

Nurses are essential in implementing clinical practice guidelines and promoting positive health outcomes. QI projects based on EBP are typically nurse-driven and provide a practical and straightforward approach to practice change (Cullen et al., 2022; Hanrahan et al., 2019). QI project leaders formulate EBP interventions by combining research evidence with best practices and patient values (Cullen et al., 2022). To help guide clinical decision-making, theoretical frameworks were used. Theoretical frameworks provided clinicians with a procedural approach to tackling a stated clinical problem; this approach allowed nurses to identify measures, study variables, develop interventions, perform outcome analysis, and evaluate implementation processes throughout the QI project (Cullen et al., 2022; Hanrahan et al., 2019; Buckwalter et al., 2017)

Integration of the Iowa Model

Although several theoretical frameworks can be utilized to direct clinical decision-making and EBP implementation, this QI project used the Iowa Model (Figure 1). As a practice model, the Iowa Model's primary goal is to direct clinicians in using evidence to enhance patient outcomes (Hanrahan et al., 2019; Buckwalter et al., 2017). It combines the systematic review and synthesis of current literature and the incorporation of other types of evidence, such as expert opinion and case reports (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Several recently published QI projects have successfully used the Iowa Model in translating research evidence into practice (Cherney et al., 2020; Melin, 2018; Servas et al., 2022). One was a standardized perioperative handoff between anesthesia providers and recovery

room nurses; the second was an educational tool for multidisciplinary tracheostomy care (Cherney et al., 2020; Servas et al., 2022). The third was a project that created an educational daily fall risk stratification tool to increase bed and chair alarm use in a medical-surgical unit (Melin, 2018). All three studies incorporated the seven Iowa Model steps in their methodologies, with pre-and post-analysis of quantitative data, evaluation of the practice changes, and knowledge dissemination (Cherney et al., 2020; Melin, 2018; Servas et al., 2022). Using the Iowa Model, the three QI projects showcased improved clinical practice and patient outcomes, positive work culture changes, and significant fiscal savings (Cherney et al., 2020; Melin, 2018; Servas et al., 2022).

The seven-step process of the Iowa Model (Figure 1) begins with a practice or knowledge-focused trigger issue that instigates the assessment of a current healthcare practice. Healthcare staff then postulates whether patient outcomes can be improved via research and evidence appraisal. Once a problem statement is specified and deemed a priority issue, a QI team reviews the literature systematically. If enough research evidence exists, EBP guidelines are applied or developed using the results from the current research in conjunction with existing clinical knowledge. Recommended methods derived from the literature are then compared to current practice to determine whether a change is necessary. If a practice change is needed, it is carried out through planned change tests, which initially involve a pilot study comprising a small number of stakeholders. The EBP guidelines are then refined using preliminary evaluation data, and the subsequent changes to clinical practice are applied to more stakeholders once deemed appropriate (Cullen et al., 2022; Hanrahan et al., 2019; Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Identifying Trigger Issues

The increasing prevalence of DM in the current population and the consequences of this disease have made the medical management of this population necessary. The adverse effects of inappropriate BG control in the DM population undergoing surgery were well-documented, and several solutions have been explored. Most anesthesia providers are aware of the harmful outcomes of DM; however, suboptimal perioperative management of this patient population still exists in many healthcare institutions.

State the Question or Purpose

This project aimed to increase anesthesia providers' compliance with intraoperative glycemic management. It identified barriers that interfered with this objective and helped propose possible solutions to improve adherence to appropriate glycemic control.

Priority

It was crucial to determine the priority of an issue when assessing and implementing change. Health record reviews initially identified inadequate BG control in a Southern California hospital. Only 3% of the Type 2 DM surgical patients undergoing two-hour or longer surgeries had their BG measured intraoperatively (Alcaraz et al., 2020). This statistic identified a significant care gap, and staff education on the Emory protocol was then carried out by Putman and Stitt (2022). Another chart review was conducted, and the results showed an increase from 14% to 39% in intraoperative BG monitoring; however, patient outcomes were unchanged regarding improved BG control (Africano et al., 2022). Therefore, a gap in patient care remained as there were persistent problems with provider compliance regarding intraoperative glycemic monitoring.

Form a Team

The team consisted of three Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) candidates from Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) and California State University Fullerton (CSUF). Two faculty professors joined them: a team lead from KPSA and a faculty mentor from CSUF. In addition, the Anesthesia Department Administrator was the point of contact for the study setting and was involved and updated throughout the project.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Body of Evidence

A literature review was initiated through PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO databases, and applicable information was appraised and synthesized. Several studies' data were found to address the project's purpose and explore the barriers to optimal glycemic care and strategies to improve perioperative glycemic management. Based on the findings, a survey regarding barriers was administered (Appendix A), and a simple alert-based tool was developed for deployment in the electronic medical record (EMR).

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

The survey assessing the barriers to glycemic management was distributed to the anesthesia staff. It consisted of four questions (Appendix A). Furthermore, information technology (IT) and informatics personnel working with the EMR were contacted for the development of a clinical decision support (CDS) tool. In surgeries lasting beyond two hours, when a diabetic patient is due for a BG check, an alert notification will pop up on the patient's anesthesia record in the EMR. The reminder will alert the anesthesia provider to measure and record a BG value in the patient's EMR. Survey data was recorded and analyzed throughout the project implementation, identifying practice barriers. This project did not include a comprehensive chart review to assess the alert-based tool's effectiveness.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

Implementing change and sustaining it is a complex and multifactorial process. Successful change requires staff accountability, continuous assessment, and reminders about appropriate glycemic guidelines. The change must be deemed effective with notable improvements to patient outcomes to receive staff acknowledgment and buy-in. Consequently, additional chart reviews and staff surveys may be necessary.

Disseminate Results

The initial defense of the project proposal was done in December 2022. The project authors implemented the methods during Spring 2023 and presented their final findings in December 2023. The project findings were disseminated to all team members, perioperative staff, and anesthesia providers. Further evaluation is required to assess the validity and sustainability of an alert-based tool. If subsequent chart audits show statistically significant improvements in compliance with intraoperative BG monitoring, the final findings and solutions can be disseminated to other regional Southern California hospitals facing similar issues.

Conclusion

Healthcare providers must deliver high-quality, cost-effective care grounded in best practices, particularly in our evolving and aging healthcare environment. EBPs, which are linked to optimal health and fiscal outcomes, are more crucial than ever (Cullen et al., 2022). The Iowa Model served as the foundation for developing and implementing this QI project, facilitated practice change through a comprehensive literature review, barrier identification, and the proposal of EBPs to improve intraoperative BG monitoring among anesthesia providers.

Review of Literature

This QI project addressed intraoperative glycemic management adherence among anesthesia providers in a Southern California hospital. The electronic databases of PubMed, EBSCO, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), and Google Scholar were used to identify articles that assessed hyperglycemia's adverse effects, barriers to BG monitoring, and practical strategies to enhance BG monitoring perioperatively. The key terms and phrases used in searching the indices were "hyperglycemia," "perioperative," "glycemic management," "glucose control," "intraoperative management of hyperglycemia," "barriers to hyperglycemia management," and "strategies for hyperglycemia control." The initial search resulted in over 1,000 articles, which then required a narrower search criterion to support the purpose of this project. The literature search was narrowed via filters using the following inclusion criteria: publication dates between 2017 and 2022, the English language, quantitative and qualitative data, and those with a high level of evidence, such as meta-analyses, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and systematic reviews. This focused approach significantly narrowed the results, yielding approximately 75 relevant studies that met these specific criteria. Despite the substantial number of articles initially identified, only a few were directly relevant to the project's objectives, as determined through abstract reviews. To further augment the literature review and bolster the project's validity, high-quality studies that were related and identified through bibliography reviews were also included.

Three randomized control trials (Piazza et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021; Ylikoski et al., 2020), two systematic reviews (Correa et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2021), one meta-analysis (Jiang et al., 2021), ten reviews (Eerdekens et al., 2020; Haque et al., 2021; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Millar et al., 2019; Morrow et al., 2022; Nair et al., 2017; Pérez et al., 2020; Pontes

et al., 2018; Simpao & Rehman, 2018; Vogt & Bally, 2020), six retrospective observational studies (Jajosky et al., 2019; Lahka et al., 2020; Nair et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2020; Shanks et al., 2018; Tollinche et al., 2020), three qualitative observational studies (Leonardsen et al., 2022; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Weng et al., 2020), one implementation project (Chen et al., 2021), two descriptive studies (Millar et al., 2019; Moyimane et al., 2017), two nonexperimental survey studies (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019), one pre-implementation mixed method study (Ayton et al., 2017), two QI projects (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; LeRiger et al., 2020), and one quasi-experimental study (Li et al., 2020) were selected with varying levels of evidence.

Findings from the articles were synthesized based on the patterns of (1) the adverse effects of intraoperative hyperglycemia, (2) barriers to BG monitoring among anesthesia providers, and (3) strategies for improving this practice deficit.

Intraoperative Hyperglycemia

Numerous factors contribute to hyperglycemia during surgery. During physiologic stress, a surge of counter-regulatory hormones (i.e., cortisol, growth hormone, glucagon), in addition to sympathetic nervous system activation, causes an excessive proinflammatory cytokine release and increased endogenous glucose production via gluconeogenesis (Dogra & Jialal, 2022; Duggan et al., 2017). These processes cause impaired insulin signaling and transient insulin resistance during the intraoperative period, which leads to hyperglycemia in patients with or without DM (Duggan et al., 2017). According to Karlet (2017), this transient stress-induced hyperglycemic response is the body's reaction to lower circulating insulin levels and is most noticeable on the first postoperative day, though it may last several days. Surgeries involving the opening of the abdominal or thoracic cavities or those under general anesthesia have been linked

to more significant and protracted hyperglycemia than laparoscopic or superficial cases or those under local or neuraxial anesthesia (Dogra & Jialal, 2022; Duggan et al., 2017).

Several studies have found a relationship between intraoperative hyperglycemia and postoperative morbidity and mortality events (Nair et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2020; Shanks et al., 2018). Although these studies were observational, all three used large sample sizes, included patients with or without a DM diagnosis, and demonstrated the need for further research. One study correlated their findings to a possible barrier to performing intraoperative BG checks among anesthesia providers (Shah et al., 2020). However, the main limitation of these studies was their retrospective nature; thus, there was a high risk of potential bias and residual confounders (Nair et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2020; Shanks et al., 2018).

Two studies investigated the relationship between intraoperative hyperglycemia and infectious complications among elective surgical patients (Nair et al., 2019; Shanks et al., 2018). The population included patients with or without DM classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) status 1 to 4. Primary outcomes included National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) morbidity events such as SSI, pneumonia, sepsis, urinary tract infection (UTI), prolonged hospital stays, or 30-day readmissions due to surgical complications. Results from the Shanks et al. (2018) study indicated that intraoperative mild ($BG \geq 150$ mg/dL) and moderate (BG 150-196 mg/dL) intraoperative hyperglycemia were independent risk factors for postoperative infectious complications. Similarly, Nair et al. (2019) concluded that mean BG levels of greater than or equal to 180 mg/dL and glycemic variability of greater than or equal to 30 mg/dL in patients with or without DM were linked to more extended hospital stays, increased mortality, and higher risk for surgical complications. However, a multicenter retrospective study confers contrasting results (Shah et al., 2020). It involved 5,014 elective surgical patients who

showed that regardless of DM status, there was no significant collinearity between adverse NSQIP events and patients with intraoperative BG levels above 180 mg/dL as opposed to those with BG levels equal to or less than 180 mg/dL. Additionally, the authors found that for patients without DM, there was no statistically significant difference in postoperative complications for BG levels at or above 150 mg/dL (Shah et al., 2020). In their discussion, the authors correlated the significance of their findings to the anesthesia provider's apprehension in treating acute intraoperative hyperglycemia. What those findings meant was that anesthesia providers might be hesitant to perform BG checks and administer intraoperative insulin to nondiabetics due to the potential risk of hypoglycemia while under anesthesia, leading to the belief that moderate to strict glyceemic control may not be beneficial for those patients (Shah et al., 2020).

The effect of intraoperative hyperglycemia on postoperative morbidity events has been well-researched. Although one study showed the lack of a statistical relationship between the two (Shah et al., 2020), several studies demonstrated a positive correlation between mild to severe hyperglycemia and poor patient outcomes postoperatively (Nair et al., 2019; Shanks et al., 2018). These findings highlighted the necessity and importance of intraoperative BG monitoring among anesthesia providers, i.e., prudent and vigilant intraoperative BG monitoring was essential to optimal glyceemic control and management (Nair et al., 2019; Shanks et al., 2018). The literature also suggested that surgical patients with DM whose BG was optimally managed experienced fewer long-term consequences, shortened hospital stays, improved quality of life, and decreased DM-related mortality (Duggan et al., 2017; Karlet, 2017). However, it was essential to note that findings from the retrospective cohort study questioned the scientific validity of the currently accepted practice of maintaining strict intraoperative BG control among non-DM patients to less than 180 mg/dL (Shah et al., 2020). Consequently, the authors alluded that this lack of

established BG protocols for nondiabetics might have caused anesthesia providers not to perform routine BG checks in this patient population (Shah et al., 2020). Nonetheless, hyperglycemia in surgical patients is linked to an increased risk of complications in both DM and non-DM patients during the perioperative period. Per the ADA and expert opinion, the recommended target for perioperative BG is less than 180 mg/dL for optimal outcomes (ADA, 2018; Chen & Duggan, 2019).

Barriers to Glycemic Management

Identifying barriers to perioperative BG control was the purpose of this QI project. Findings from quantitative observational study surveys could be used to identify perceived barriers to BG control (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019). Even with the current studies, there was insufficient data or knowledge on BG control barriers (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019). However, the existing literature uncovered common themes of preventing BG control, including hypoglycemia risks with BG correction, protocol awareness, and lack of resources.

Three review studies and a prospective cohort study found fear of iatrogenic hypoglycemia was a significant barrier to the implementation of a glycemic control protocol (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020). Severe hypoglycemia, BG <40 mg/dL, increased risks of adverse side effects like comas and seizures (Eerdeken et al., 2020). Because of those side effects, Eerdeken et al. (2020) found that hospitals were less inclined to implement a strict glycemic control protocol (BG <140 mg/dL). Two reviews concluded maintaining normoglycemia was important for preventing altered organ functions (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020). However, the main problem was the lack of a well-defined BG protocol to determine whether to treat with insulin (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020). With a well-defined and moderate glycemic control protocol (BG level

between 150 and 200 mg/dL), the potential for adequately controlled blood sugar levels without a high risk of hypoglycemia is possible (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020; Pontes et al., 2018; Sathya et al., 2013).

Another barrier discovered was how a protocol for glucose control was not adequately used, and clinicians were unaware of the serious adverse effects of dysglycemia. This barrier was briefly mentioned in one implementation project, a qualitative observational study, a prospective cohort study, and four reviews when discussing how proper blood sugar limits were not set, leading to confusion on which BG levels to treat; the complete omission of BG treatment, even when it was warranted, was also seen (Chen et al., 2021; Eerdeken et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020).

The ADA (2018) defined appropriate glucose levels in critically ill patients as 140 to 180 mg/dL with the initiation of insulin treatment when the BG level was above 180 mg/dL. Based on three reviews' findings, however, the issue had been hypoglycemia caused by strict glucose control (BG <140 mg/dL), leading to a lack of compliance with protocols in the hospital regarding BG control (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018). An implementation project and systematic metareview found that there was no user-friendly protocol in place and found how implementing clinical practice guidelines could lack clarity and usability (Chen et al., 2021; Correa et al., 2020). This discrepancy led to the omission of these guidelines since clinicians either did not agree or could not understand how to use them, which was emphasized in an additional review study regarding BG targets (Chen et al., 2021; Correa et al., 2020; Pontes et al., 2018). A qualitative observation study found a lack of response to abnormal BG findings from the omission of BG reporting and a lack of awareness of managing diabetic patients (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019). The researchers observed 13 scenarios where

clinicians did not express their concerns or comment on the hyperglycemic state of the patient and five additional instances where there was a lack of knowledge on how to treat these patients (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019).

The availability and costs of supplies for proper implementation of inpatient diabetic management were found to be barriers (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017). A qualitative, exploratory, phenomenological, descriptive-style study, a pre-implementation study, and two survey clinical trials found it more challenging to manage patients appropriately due to a lack of sufficient resources (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017). In the qualitative, exploratory, phenomenological, descriptive-style study, the nursing staff reported that only one glucometer was available, and the equipment frequently failed, leading to increased incidences of poorly controlled BG levels and poor patient management (Moyimane et al., 2017). These findings resonated with the nonexperimental survey study and qualitative study that reported limited access to resources hindering the use and compliance with practice guidelines (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019). The qualitative study and a different review also found that a considerable percentage of people (20%) worried about the increased costs of implementing protocols due to the need for supplies and adequate training and increased costs for inpatient diabetic management (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Haque et al., 2021). However, Haque et al. (2021) discovered that increased costs from complicated hospital admissions due to uncontrolled BG levels (>200 mg/dL) had been far more expensive. Hospitals creating an inpatient diabetic management service were the most cost-effective and safe way to treat hyperglycemic events (Haque et al., 2021).

Limitations of the review studies regarding the resulting hypoglycemic events from BG correction included limited follow-up, resulting in an inadequate ability to assess the durability of the process change (Eerdekens et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020). A systematic metareview, implementation project, and review study shared similar limitations in that there needed to be more research and clinical trials to assess the accuracy of the results found within their studies (Chen et al., 2021; Correa et al., 2020; Pontes et al., 2018). Conversely, the implementation project had enough data to conclude a better way to manage BG management would be improved by the implementation of a hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia protocol that was easy to use and had a more moderate BG control target (BG <180 mg/dL) that was well-defined and easy to use for all specialties (ADA, 2018; Chen et al., 2021). There was also sufficient evidence from all the articles that the proper implementation of a glycemic management protocol should be emphasized in any patient care setting (Chen et al., 2021; Correa et al., 2020; Eerdekens et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020; Pontes et al., 2018).

A lack of generalizability in four studies weakened their utility (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Haque et al., 2021; Moyimane et al., 2017; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019). The level of evidence for the articles varied from Level III-V. Five similar studies also found there was a biased small sample size, which contributed to the lack of generalizability for the study (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Haque et al., 2021; Moyimane et al., 2017; Ylikoski et al., 2020). However, the clinical trial possessed strengths in having a high level of evidence, including a homogenous study population, a real-world setting, accurate BG testing measures, and a high daily rate of BG testing by staff (Ylikoski et al., 2020). The survey response rates for two separate studies found a low response rate and non-responder bias (Chui et al., 2019; Morrow et al., 2022). Chui et al. (2019) believed a strength of their research was reaching the target

audience (anesthesiologists) for their survey response, accurately depicting the perceived barrier by these clinicians. In summary, a consistent theme in the literature identifies a lack of necessary resources to adequately intervene and/or a clear BG protocol as barriers to optimum glycemic management (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Ylikoski et al., 2020).

Strategies for Glycemic Control

Researchers explored strategies for practice changes and solutions for perioperative glycemic management. The current literature supported education and collaboration, CDS systems, and alert-based tools as promising options.

Education and individualized training allowed for the successful implementation of practice changes. Two studies found the importance of education and training when employing a glycemic control protocol (Chen et al., 2021; Weng et al., 2020). One observational study explored the effectiveness of physician-centered education on glycemic control and found that targeted training improved the management of diabetic patients across 71 hospitals (Weng et al., 2020). In the implementation project, Chen et al. (2021) examined healthcare records for compliance with perioperative management of surgical patients with diabetes and then implemented and assessed evidence-based practice changes. Chen et al. (2021) identified a lack of staff education as a massive barrier to protocol implementation and created strategies that included an education package, face-to-face training sessions, and the distribution of relevant handouts (Chen et al., 2021). The follow-up audits showed a 42% increase in compliance for checking intraoperative BG if the procedure was longer than one hour (Chen et al., 2021).

Several studies emphasized the importance of a collective effort and buy-in from multiple departments and staff to apply clinical process changes successfully and adopt novel technologies (Chen et al., 2021; Millar et al., 2019; Vogt & Bally, 2020). Chen et al. (2021) continued to highlight how the involvement of multiple disciplines was crucial to effect and sustain change. The two other reviews explored published evidence on the care of diabetic patients undergoing surgery and discussed strategies for clinical management (Millar et al., 2019; Vogt & Bally, 2020). They emphasized the importance of multidisciplinary collaborations to address the intricacies of perioperative glucose management (Millar et al., 2019; Vogt & Bally, 2020). The appointment of a clinical lead responsible for identifying high-risk patients and ensuring optimal diabetes management for surgery was another identified strategy (Millar et al., 2019). The possible benefits of updating current processes with technology and tools such as safety checklists, early warning scoring alerts, computerized decision support systems, and continuous glucose monitoring were also highlighted (Millar et al., 2019; Vogt & Bally, 2020).

A CDS system is a computer system that helps healthcare providers with clinical decision-making (Nair et al., 2017). The first intraoperative CDS provided clinicians with a visual or audible alarm when the patient's heart rate was abnormal (Nair et al., 2017). Several studies showed how CDS systems could improve patient care and safety, and some specifically investigated the efficacy of different CDS systems with anesthesia and perioperative glycemic management (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Leonardsen et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021; Simpao & Rehman, 2018).

In a QI project and a quasi-experimental study, researchers found that an automatic system improved multiple aspects of glycemic management, such as increasing intraoperative BG monitoring and insulin administration (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020). The results

also showed decreased rates of patients arriving at the Post Anesthesia Care Unit (PACU) with hyperglycemia (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020). Pichardo-Lowden et al. (2021) used a qualitative observational design to test a real-time CDS tool that offered recommendations and notifications about diabetic management. The CDS tool reduced hyperglycemia in DM patients and patients with stress hyperglycemia and decreased inappropriate insulin use (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021).

CDS tools can be incorporated into practice through anesthesia information management systems (AIMS). AIMS are specialized forms of EMR systems that allow automatic and reliable collection, storage, and presentation of patient data (Simpao & Rehman, 2018). The information can be customized to offer CDS to anesthesia providers and help with clinical processes like patient care, documentation, and resources. Researchers reviewed CDS within AIMS and found strong evidence that CDS improved compliance with prophylactic antibiotic administration and clinical documentation (Simpao & Rehman, 2018). Similarly, a qualitative study was conducted to examine the perspectives of anesthesia personnel on implementing and using digital AIMS (Leonardsen et al., 2022). The participants credited AIMS for increased vigilance during anesthesia and improved collaboration and responsibility between all anesthesia providers (Leonardsen et al., 2022).

Alert-based tools are a subset of CDS systems that can be easily implemented in EMRs (Nair et al., 2017). Numerous studies showed the efficacy of an alert as a simple intervention to increase provider compliance with medication administration, documentation, and adherence to respective protocols and guidelines (LeRiger et al., 2020; Lahka et al., 2020; Jajosky et al., 2019; Piazza et al., 2020; Tollinche et al., 2020).

Researchers developed alerts to assist providers with the appropriate use of anticoagulation (Jajosky et al., 2019; Piazza et al., 2020). Jajosky et al. (2019) created an EMR alert to promote the safe administration of neuraxial analgesia in anticoagulated patients. Data from this retrospective study revealed that inappropriate anticoagulation in patients with epidural catheters was reduced by 61% (Jajosky et al., 2019). Piazza et al. (2020) conducted a randomized controlled trial to assess the impact of an alert-based CDS for high-risk patients with atrial fibrillation who required anticoagulation therapy. The alert increased anticoagulation prescriptions in these patients and decreased adverse cardiovascular events such as stroke and myocardial infarctions (Piazza et al., 2020).

The utilization of alert-based tools has also improved the documentation of pertinent information. Tollinche et al. (2020) analyzed the implementation of an alert system on documentation within the electronic anesthesia record. The retrospective study's results showed a significant increase in the documentation of essential anesthesia events with a single notification (Tollinche et al., 2020).

Researchers assessed the impact of alerts on provider compliance with perioperative standards (Lahka et al. 2020; LeRiger et al. 2020). Lahka et al. (2020) used a retrospective observational study to investigate the effect of electronic alerts on compliance with perioperative temperature management. Implementation of this alert-based CDS tool significantly increased intraoperative compliance (Lahka et al., 2020). The QI project by LeRiger et al. (2020) was implemented to increase intraoperative antibiotic redosing compliance through a specific reminder in the EMR. The data showed that implementing an organizational guideline, education, pertinent handouts, and a new EMR alert significantly increased compliance (LeRiger et al., 2020).

The literature discussed in the strategies had various limitations. A few studies utilized research designs that were considered lower levels of evidence, such as QI projects and literature reviews (Chen et al., 2021; LeRiger et al., 2020; Millar et al., 2019; Simpao & Rehman, 2018; Vogt & Bally, 2020). Studies with poor research designs threaten the validity of the findings with limited literature search strategies, insufficient sample sizes, inconclusive findings, and various biases. There were notable flaws like selection bias, confounder bias, and the Hawthorne effect that may have affected the results (Chen et al., 2021; Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Weng et al., 2020). The included reviews were also subject to evidence selection and ideological biases as specific topics were briefly touched upon while others were extensively discussed (Millar et al., 2019; Simpao & Rehman, 2018; Vogt & Bally, 2020). The generalizability of the findings was another limitation because of differences in practice standards and how some of the studies utilized information from other countries (Lahka et al., 2020; Leonardsen et al., 2022; Millar et al., 2019; Tollinche et al., 2020). The studies with higher levels of evidence also noted design flaws that include insufficient sample size, lack of blinding, improper data collection, inadequate analysis, unadjusted data, and/or skewed results (Jajosky et al., 2019); Leonardsen et al., 2022; Li et al. 2020; Piazza et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021). LeRiger et al. (2020) stated limitations around dissemination and communication about appropriate guidelines for their change implementation.

Despite the limitations of the studies included in this ROL, they are helpful and, as a body, offer the best evidence on possible strategies to improve glycemic control. The review articles were considered good quality as experts introduced new concepts, revealed inconsistencies in current research, synthesized the vast results, and provided an informative snapshot of the topics (Vogt & Bally, 2020; Millar et al., 2019; Simpao & Rehman, 2018).

Likewise, the findings with statistically significant data indicated that an observed association is unlikely due to chance (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020; Tollinche et al., 2020; Weng et al., 2020; Ehrenfeld et al., 2017). Several studies also incorporated robust designs that delivered high levels of evidence and minimized threats to study validity (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021; Lahka et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Piazza et al., 2020; Tollinche et al., 2020; Weng et al., 2020).

Conclusion

This literature review outlined the importance of anesthesia providers' role in intraoperative glycemic control. A BG protocol keeping BG <180 mg/dL was shown to help reduce the occurrence of hyperglycemia without the frequent hypoglycemia seen in BG protocols with tight targets (e.g., 120 mg/dL). Using a CDS alert-based tool promoted by a unit champion could further increase the compliance of BG monitoring intraoperatively. While follow-up education, compliance surveys, alert tool implementation, and reassessment of hyperglycemia could not be completed in the timeline of this project, the assessment of barriers with a survey and the creation of a reminder pop-up were further explained in the results section of this paper.

Methods

This study was a continuation of an ongoing QI project to improve intraoperative glycemic management among anesthesia providers in a Southern California hospital. First, our team distributed a survey (Appendix A) that offered a tool for discovering barriers to following an established DM treatment protocol (Putman & Stitt, 2022). Afterward, our team proposed interventions addressing any obstacles to care identified from the responses from the barrier survey. Our team also introduced an evidence-based CDS alert tool. The tool's impact on the BG test by anesthesia providers will need to be assessed via a chart audit at a future date (Appendix B); analysis regarding the efficacy of the CDS alert tool is beyond this project's scope. Data from the barrier survey was statistically analyzed and incorporated, with the results and outcomes assessed in the Results section.

Design

The primary design for this QI project was a qualitative descriptive study design. A barriers survey was electronically distributed to anesthesia providers (certified registered nurse anesthetists [CRNAs] and anesthesiologists) at the pilot study site over eight weeks between July 2023 and August 2023. The main reason for using this study design was the subjective nature of this project and the lack of peer-reviewed 'barrier tools' that evaluate intraoperative glycemic monitoring among anesthesia providers in the literature. A benefit of a qualitative descriptive approach is that it allows the collection of descriptive experiences and perceptions regarding a phenomenon where the research topic is not well-known (Doyle et al., 2020). The barriers survey, consisting of four questions, answered two key questions for this project: (1) "*What are the barriers to intraoperative BG monitoring?*" and (2) "*How can this practice be improved?*" The complete barriers survey can be accessed in Appendix A.

Setting

The pilot site of this QI project was a 262-bed community Southern California hospital that serves twenty-four communities (i.e., towns, counties, or zip codes). The top three ethnicities served in this community hospital include Hispanic/Latino (44.94%), White (30.87%), and Asian (19.72%). Socioeconomic data revealed that 14.57% of the population lived below the federal poverty level, while 14.96% were uninsured (Kaiser Foundation Hospital: Anaheim and Irvine, 2020).

Anesthesia providers, consisting of thirty-nine CRNAs and sixty-one physician anesthesiologists, provide perioperative care for various surgeries that include—but are not limited to—general, neurological, orthopedic, and gynecological across ten operating rooms. It is important to note that these providers are employed by the regional hospital system and routinely rotate or ‘float’ between two distinct hospitals that comprise the pilot site. Intraoperatively, anesthesia providers collect and manually enter point-of-care BG data in the patient's EMR, which is handed off to nurses in the recovery area postoperatively (Africano et al., 2022).

Participants

Convenience sampling was utilized to recruit survey participants. The survey was designed to collect data exclusively from anesthesia providers, excluding non-anesthesia personnel, such as operating room nurses, surgeons, and scrub technicians, as well as non-provider roles in anesthesia, such as anesthesia technicians. Out of one hundred anesthesia providers, twenty-five completed the project's barriers survey.

Ethical Considerations

This project strictly followed the ethical principles related to human and social research. The participants were notified of their rights, including confidentiality, informed consent, and

anonymity. They were made aware of their ability to withdraw from the project and abstain from answering questions without consequences. An exemption from the Institutional Review Boards of Kaiser Permanente Southern California and CSUF, was obtained for this QI project. The Institutional Review Boards approved the original project for chart reviews, compliance monitoring, and provider education implementation and evaluation (Alcaraz et al., 2020; Putman & Stitt, 2022).

Measures

For this project, the measures considered the step-by-step procedural approach on when the implementation was conducted, what tools were used, how data was collected, and discussed the planned interventions based on the data collection. After a discussion with the project's team lead, it was established that the primary goal of this project was to achieve a minimum response rate of 20% from the barriers survey. Another goal was implementing the CDS alert “pop-up” within the EMR.

Procedure

Following the approval from the Institutional Review Board of California State University, Fullerton (Appendix F) and the exemption from the Institutional Review Board of Kaiser Permanente Southern California (Appendix E), the QI project was introduced to the pilot site, in which a detailed discussion about the barrier survey was held via Zoom on July 18th, 2023. Subsequently, the barrier survey (Appendix A) was emailed to the anesthesia providers. Weekly reminders were sent via email throughout the survey period to encourage participation. In addition to evaluating barriers to protocol compliance, a CDS alert tool to notify providers to check patient BG levels was being developed in collaboration with the EMR manufacturer and integrated healthcare system IT Department. The tool is meant to “pop-up” when an anesthesia

provider cares for a DM patient in a case longer than two hours. Implementation of this tool will take place in the future as it is still in the development and approval phase with the pilot site's IT department and chief stakeholders. Chart audits to determine the impact of the interventions may be conducted following CDS deployment and mitigation of barriers to care identified in this project's questionnaire.

Data Collection

Qualtrics, an online survey platform, was used in this QI project to gather qualitative data from anesthesia providers regarding the barriers to perioperative glucose management. It offered the creation of a four-item barrier survey, which was electronically disseminated to the pilot site via a quick-response (QR) code. The four questions within the survey were: *(1) What are potential barriers to appropriate perioperative hyperglycemic management? (2) Please elaborate on the answers in question one and/or note other barriers to care; (3) What are some suggestions to improve perioperative glucose management? (4) Would a reminder "pop-up" (clinical decision support tool) in HealthConnect be useful?*

These questions were based on the literature findings and expert opinion. Three review studies and a cohort study found an important barrier to following a blood glucose protocol was the risk for unintended hypoglycemia (Eerdeken et al., 2020; Haque et al., 2021; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020). Seven similar studies found that lack of awareness of protocols or confusing protocols were barriers to providers staying compliant with existing protocols (Chen et al., 2021; Eerdeken et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020). One study found that the omission of hyperglycemic events occurred due to confusion or unawareness of glycemic protocols (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019). Lastly, six studies found that due to a lack of resources, protocol

compliance was poor (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017). Based on the previous cohorts' conclusions, these findings hold significance because there was already a noticeable lack of compliance at the pilot site. The survey helped determine the barriers to noncompliance, which was discussed further in the Results section.

Interventions

While completing the barriers survey, the first intervention was developing a CDS alert tool with the IT department in the integrated healthcare system. The barriers survey helped identify the usefulness of a CDS alert tool by asking, “*Would a CDS alert tool in the EMR help you remember to check patients’ BG levels?*” The literature also showed that a CDS alert tool could increase protocol compliance. Lakha et al. (2020) found the use of a CDS tool to improve the performance of intraoperative targeted normothermia by 43%, and LeRiger et al. (2020) found improved compliance with antibiotic therapy protocols after implementing an antibiotic EMR alert tool. The CDS alert tool for this project focused on alerting anesthesia providers on the need to check their patient's BG levels every two hours as specified in the management protocol. Six months after the CDS is deployed, a follow-up chart audit should be performed to evaluate the efficacy of the CDS. The CDS alert tool is essential, but additional interventions and recommendations may be considered based on the results from the barriers survey.

Data Analysis and Evaluation

The project authors used NVivo, a software known for its qualitative data analysis capabilities, to facilitate the analysis of open-ended survey responses. This tool organized and coded the responses within a single project file, allowing for a comprehensive comparison. NVivo's inductive coding approach was vital in identifying the main themes from the open-

ended questions (Appendix A), as it enabled thematic narrative synthesis, revealing patterns and themes. Its selection of visualization options, including graphs and frequency plots (Appendix H, Figures 4 and 5), enhanced the team's data analysis. Thematic analysis was instrumental in identifying recurring themes within qualitative data and is often recommended for novice researchers (Elliott-Mainwaring, 2021). The exploration of such underlying themes contributed to the evidence-based recommendations on how to improve glycemic management at the pilot site.

Results

The results of this QI project effectively address the project's purpose and aim, which was to enhance adherence to intraoperative glucose management among anesthesia providers at the pilot site. Conducted from July to August 2023, the survey garnered responses from twenty-five anesthesia providers, achieving the team's target response rate of at least 20%. As revealed through the survey responses, identifying key barriers to perioperative glycemetic management aligns with the project's continuation of previous efforts in auditing and implementing interventions for improved glucose management.

In addition to identifying barriers, the following discovered themes, as encoded by NVivo, were integral to the project's analysis and discussion and offered a comprehensive view of the challenges in perioperative glycemetic management. These themes were: (1) limited access to supplies, (2) personnel-related challenges, (3) protocol unfamiliarity, and (4) automated EMR reminders.

Limited Access to Supplies

As indicated by 46.15% of respondents (Appendix H, Figure 2), a significant barrier was limited access to supplies. One respondent stated, "*Glucometers are hard to come by.*" Another highlighted, "*We only have one glucometer for all ORs so having more units would help.*" Additional responses included frustrations over "*cumbersome machine and supplies,*" "*cumbersome strip testing,*" and "*no access code.*" Another pointed out that there was "*No glycometer [sic] in the operating room. Must wait for someone to bring [a] machine to [the] operating room.*" The restrictive system was also criticized: "*Restrictive system on having the glucometer checked, available, and all providers credentialed.*" Practical suggestions to alleviate

this burden were to *"have a glucose monitor in every OR"* and to ensure *"more glucometers, ideally one for every OR in Pyxis/Cart."*

Personnel-Related Challenges

Approximately 31% of survey respondents (Appendix H, Figure 2) identified personnel-related challenges as a significant barrier in perioperative glycemic management. The issues included difficulties in maintaining access to glucometers and credentialing.

Several respondents expressed frustration about gaining access to necessary equipment: *"Despite using [a] glucometer routinely, one gets locked out. Then [I] have to do the online learning module and have to be credentialed to use [a] glucometer. Difficult to maintain access."* A similar sentiment was: *"Glucometers have ridiculously short certification validity windows before needing recertification."* Two responses pointed out the need for a simplified process: *"Would be grateful to have regular help with having my NUID accepted by the glucometer"* and *"Ensuring control checks are completed, appropriate ID numbers are available."*

Furthermore, the difficulty imposed by certification processes was highlighted: *"Kaiser lab makes it extremely hard for [a] physician to certify to do glucose yet. Not enough glucose yet [sic]."* This statement indicates a potential disconnect between the pilot site's processes and the practical needs of anesthesia providers.

Finally, suggestions for simplifying the process were mentioned: *"Have the glucometer be able to accept everyone's NUID."* The potential role of anesthesia technologists in routine tasks was highlighted: *"It would help if anesthesia techs performed the daily quality control testing on machines."* These responses echoed the need for a more streamlined process that accommodates all operating room personnel without repetitive credentialing and a collaborative

approach to equipment management, potentially easing the burden on anesthesia providers.

Protocol Unfamiliarity

Several (23.08%) respondents indicated unfamiliarity with the Emory protocol (Appendix H, Figure 2). Respondents highlighted the inadequacy of published protocols and the need for improvements. One provider expressed concern about the risks involved: *"Too much uncertainty... I fear a patient will exit my care with too much risk of hypoglycemia..."* Another provider shared their proactive approach: *"I already have created a pop-up on my macro for this but limit it to pts [sic] concurrently on insulin with orders from/to ICU or floor. Simply adding to order sets is not sufficient either - orders get missed or delayed frequently."* One response simply suggested: *"Have [a] standardized treatment protocol."* These comments underscore the risks associated with the lack of protocol familiarity and its inconsistent application, highlighting the importance of education.

Automated EMR Reminders

A substantial portion of the respondents, 87.5% (Appendix H, Figure 3), acknowledged the advantages of incorporating technological solutions into the existing EMR system. Among the twenty-five respondents, twenty-one expressed a desire to integrate a reminder tool into the EMR, and only three disagreed. One respondent emphasized its utility: *"Reminders in [the] intraop[erative] [EMR] to check glucose in a timely manner will be helpful."* Another respondent resonated with this sentiment, suggesting a more specific implementation: *"Pop-up reminders in [the electronic] chart."* These responses stress the need for automated EMR reminders, ensuring that BG checks are not overlooked during elective surgeries lasting beyond two hours.

The themes of limited access to supplies, personnel-related challenges, protocol unfamiliarity, and the need for automated EMR reminders, as identified through NVivo, not only reflected the current state of existing challenges at the study site but also proposed evidence-based solutions to overcome them. These results were instrumental in guiding future interventions and strategies to increase provider compliance to ensure better patient outcomes in perioperative glycemic management.

Discussion

The project's primary aims were to identify barriers in perioperative glycemic management and propose interventions to enhance provider adherence to the established protocol. A key goal was achieving a considerable survey response rate, with the target set at a minimum of 20%. The project surpassed this target, securing a 25% response rate. This level of participation is considered suitable for qualitative analysis, especially in surveys with smaller sample sizes, such as those with less than 500 participants (Wu et al., 2022). According to Fosnacht et al. (2017) and Wu et al. (2022), a response rate within the range of 20% to 25% is necessary to ensure a meaningful evaluation of qualitative findings.

This project provided insights into common barriers anesthesia providers believed to affect perioperative glycemic management at the pilot site. Two significant barriers were discovered, including adequate access to supplies and personnel-related issues. Several research studies supported these findings of protocol challenges and insufficient resources as obstacles to effective glycemic management. Multiple studies discovered inappropriate protocol usage due to confusion about the implementation of the protocol and its treatment modalities (Chen et al., 2021; Eerdeken et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020). Similarly, other studies found that adhering to glycemic protocols was challenging when hospital resources, such as equipment availability and maintenance, funding for supplies and training, were scarce (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Ayton et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2022; Moyimane et al., 2017). In addition, the previous projects about an educational intervention for anesthesia providers and an assessment of provider compliance with the implemented glycemic management protocol also

observed factors such as protocol and clinician-specific workplace issues that contributed to inadequate glycemic management (Putman & Stitt, 2022; Africano et al., 2022).

In examining the barriers identified in this QI study, it is important to consider the unique operational dynamics and resource allocation at the study site. As highlighted by the survey, the significant issues of inadequate access to supplies and personnel-related challenges may stem from the facility's specific budget and workforce distribution constraints. This interpretation aligns with the findings of Ambulkar et al. (2017) and Chui et al. (2019), who noted similar challenges in settings with limited resources.

The demographic and socioeconomic makeup of the pilot site's community offers vital information to interpret the identified barriers to perioperative glycemic management. There is a diverse ethnic composition with a significant Hispanic/Latino population and a notable percentage of patients living below the poverty line or uninsured, likely influencing the challenges to perioperative glycemic management (Kaiser Foundation Hospital: Anaheim and Irvine, 2020). These socioeconomic factors may contribute to the issues of inadequate access to supplies, as financial constraints and insurance coverage gaps could affect the availability and allocation of resources within the pilot site. This aligns with the findings of Chui et al. (2019) and Haque et al. (2021), who noted resource limitations in similar settings but added a layer of complexity given the diverse needs and potential health disparities faced by the study site's patient population.

Conversely, the survey results did not reflect concerns about hypoglycemia as a barrier to the implementation of a glucose control protocol as described in three related studies (Eerdekens et al., 2020; Pérez et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018). Eerdekens et al. (2020) studied tight glucose control in patients in ICUs on insulin drips who had their BG levels checked less

frequently (>1 hour), resulting in hypoglycemic episodes. The other two studies had a similar sample size to Eerdeken et al. (2020), where they found patients on an insulin infusion more likely to have episodes of hypoglycemia than those treated with a basal-bolus insulin strategy (Pérez et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018). These differing sample populations can explain why survey responders did not believe or witness frequent episodes of hypoglycemia since patients coming in for noncardiac surgery are not usually placed on an insulin drip.

The survey showed that an overwhelming majority believed a reminder "pop-up" in the EMR would increase compliance among anesthesia providers. Multiple research studies support the belief that a CDS tool is a viable solution for increasing BG monitoring, leading to appropriate insulin administration, and reducing hyperglycemia (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021). Therefore, a CDS tool in the form of a simple reminder "pop-up" was proposed for the pilot site. A decision support tool that facilitates effective glycemic management is being developed to meet the hospital's standards and will be trialed.

It is important to note that the proposed solution of implementing a reminder 'pop-up' in the EMR reflects the need for an understanding of the practice patterns of anesthesia providers. This tool, supported by Ehrenfeld et al. (2017) and Li et al. (2020), suggests a promising intervention for enhancing protocol compliance. However, its effectiveness hinges on the nuanced understanding of how providers interact with the EMR system at the pilot site. The cultural practices of the CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists that float between two separate hospitals may complicate the implementation of consistent glycemic management protocols. The variability in provider familiarity with the specific protocols of each hospital could contribute to the personnel-related issues identified in the survey. This situation is somewhat distinct from the general findings in the literature, such as those by Pichardo-Lowden et al. (2021), which may not

fully account for the challenges posed by a floating provider workforce. Therefore, the proposed CDS alert tool must be designed to accommodate the unique workflow and cultural practices of this diverse and mobile provider group. Its implementation should consider the varying levels of familiarity between the two hospitals within the pilot site among providers who may not consistently work at one.

The perceptions of barriers in this project's survey were relatively consistent with the other research studies. Such results emphasized the importance of utilizing strategies that focus on solving the reoccurring issues of lack of resources, inconsistent practices among personnel, and unfamiliar treatment protocols.

Recommendations

Survey responses provided valuable data on potential inefficiencies and suggestions for improved glycemic management interventions. The survey results echoed previous research on implementation barriers, and improvement strategies gleaned from similar studies can be applied and are discussed below.

The appointment of glycemic management champions will help the pilot site mitigate various barriers to glycemic control and sustain change. Champions are individuals who support, advocate, and spearhead an implementation initiative while overcoming resistance that may occur (Morena et al., 2022). They are vital in reducing provider implementation barriers and promoting behavior change (Morena et al., 2022). Reynolds et al. (2022) used clinical champions to implement education, visual aids, and real-time feedback to sustain interventions that reduced catheter-associated urinary tract infections. The perioperative glycemic management champions will liaise for this QI project and be briefed and updated on all relevant information.

The barrier of limited supply access suggested supply chain and distribution logistics issues. This barrier can be addressed with personnel responsible for providing equipment such as glucometers, testing strips, and insulin to the operating rooms. Aside from anesthesia providers, additional staff members can also be accountable for the glucometer testing of surgical patients. Potential staff assisting anesthesia providers in measuring blood glucose include anesthesiology technicians, operating room nurses, and clinicians assigned as break relief. The champions can also work with the leads of the anesthesiology and surgical departments to ensure that the staff maintains their required glucometer competency training and the supplies are fully stocked. Accountability, collaboration, and awareness among hospital staff can foster appropriate glycemic management across multiple disciplines and better use of resources (Pirchardo-Lowden et al., 2019).

Other barriers identified by survey participants were personnel-related (e.g., forgetting to check the BG) and lack of familiarity with the Emory protocol. These survey responses show the importance of adequate training, competency checks, and visual reminders for all anesthesia providers. Along with the automated EMR reminder, an annual education refresher on the glycemic management protocol and visual protocol aids attached to the anesthesia workstations can help with compliance and ensure consistent application (Reynolds et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021; Weng et al., 2020). Putman and Stitt (2022) previously created an educational program on the Emory protocol for anesthesia providers. The materials from the program, a virtual presentation, and digital index cards of guidelines can be used to reinforce provider practice gaps. The glycemic champions can be resources and points of contact when confusion and issues regarding the protocol arise among staff (Morena et al., 2022).

Most respondents agreed that a reminder "pop-up" in the EMR would be beneficial. The positive opinion regarding an automated reminder shows a collective inclination towards leveraging technology to enhance compliance and improve clinical outcomes. Technological advances have improved healthcare aspects like provider compliance and correct protocol usage (Lahka et al., 2020; LeRiger et al., 2020). Chart audits would need to be conducted in the future to evaluate the effectiveness of the CDS tool after implementation.

Implications for Practice

The findings of this project can serve as the foundation for practice change by implementing tools and protocols that will help increase sustainability, improve compliance, and reduce complications seen with poorly controlled BG levels. Enhancing providers' compliance with perioperative glycemic management protocols is imperative through education, access to supplies, CDS tool implementation, and protocol implementation.

Lack of education is a significant roadblock in proper BG management. Research revealed that after implementing education, compliance with BG management increased by 42% (Chen et al., 2021). A different study also found that targeted training on glycemic control improved the management of DM patients across 71 hospitals (Weng et al., 2020). Hospital administrators are impacted because they need to provide sufficient education to the staff and ensure compliance. Education benefits anesthesia providers by helping them understand the importance of BG management and how it can be correctly managed. Education has been shown to primarily affect compliance depending on the knowledge someone has on the topic (Rua et al., 2022). Knowledge has also been linked directly to positive outcomes (Rua et al., 2022). Moreover, well-educated staff are more likely to adhere to established protocols, ensuring long-

term benefits in patient care. By implementing education within institutions for anesthesia providers, compliance with BG protocols and proper management can significantly increase.

Protocol implementation is another vital method for reducing complications and creating compliance. Huwyler (2018) stated that a strong compliance culture starts with setting expectations through policies and protocols that hold people accountable. Several articles also found that due to a lack of a protocol, there were no clear standards on how to manage patients, leading to poor patient management (Chen et al., 2021; Eerdeken et al., 2020; Iqbal & Heller, 2018; Pérez et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2018; Ylikoski et al., 2020). These findings, along with the input from the anesthesia providers at the pilot site, helped identify that a simple protocol implementation emphasized with education can benefit compliance and sustainability of BG management by setting clear standards and expectations.

Improving access to supplies (e.g. insulin, glucometers) will increase provider compliance to proper DM patient management. Several studies highlighted how providers cannot follow through with compliance and create a sustainable practice model without adequate access to supplies (Ambulkar et al., 2017; Chui et al., 2019). Ensuring sufficient access to supplies is a matter of improving care and aligning with sustainability. By working with administrators, a possible solution can be found that helps grant access to the equipment needed (e.g., glucometers, insulin) and combat the negative attributes associated with the lack of supplies.

The usefulness of a CDS alert tool was an important finding. Specific studies stated that implementing a CDS alert tool can achieve compliance with protocol awareness and proper patient management (Ehrenfeld et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020; Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021). This is due to reducing personnel errors with forgetfulness found within the survey as a current barrier at the pilot site. Additionally, this tool can be vital in sustaining compliance through timely

reminders reducing medical errors and costs associated with improper glycemic management. With the implementation of the tool within the EMR, compliance can be evaluated via a chart audit to prove the survey and literature findings are accurate.

The literature review and the findings from this QI project can be used to help improve the current practices in place for BG management of DM patients by outlining the barriers found. The findings are not only useful in terms of immediate patient care, but it also aligns with the broader goal of a sustainable healthcare practice. Further studies will need to be conducted to legitimize the perceived implications for practice and whether the CDS alert tool is enough to make an impact.

Strengths and Limitations

This QI project had its share of strengths and limitations. A strong literature review serves as the foundation for research projects and helps increase generalizability, relevance, originality, and impact on the targeted population of the study (Maggio et al., 2016). The review of literature for this QI project was strong in that it contained thirty-two articles, and fourteen of them were related to barriers to glycemic management. One of the aims of this QI project was to understand the perceived barriers to glycemic control through the distribution of a barriers survey to the anesthesia providers at the pilot site. High-quality survey questions were developed by analyzing and extracting information from the literature to help determine the cause of poor glycemic management (Maggio et al., 2016).

The qualitative design of studies helps understand the “how” and “why” in research (Cleland, 2017). While quantitative research is important, qualitative research helps understand the reality of what is happening with a group of people or within an institution (Cleland, 2017). Since this project focused on why patients in the perioperative setting did not have their BG

levels checked, using a qualitative survey helped understand the “why” and helped pinpoint possible solutions and interventions to the perceived barriers. Qualitative studies can capture experiences, attitudes, and behaviors in a study more accurately than quantitative studies (Tenny et al., 2022). This aspect of qualitative studies was evident in this QI project by the insight gained from participants' perspectives. The participants at the pilot site were some of the key players in understanding the “why” of the problem. By targeting the anesthesia providers and their opinions with the barriers survey, themes and patterns guided the researchers to the possible solutions to the problem. Qualitative studies also allow for much flexibility with the study design. Structures can be constructed and reconstructed depending on the findings and what applies to the pilot site of the study (Rahman, 2016). This quality of the study allowed for the creation of the CDS alert tool once the participants of the barrier survey confirmed that it would be helpful in perioperative BG management. The creation of the CDS alert tool is another strength of this study because these tools have been shown to improve patient care and increase protocol compliance (Pichardo-Lowden et al., 2021).

Another strength of this QI project was it was a pilot study for assessing the barriers to BG control, which did not occur before the implementation of this project. Pilot studies are important to the main study by contributing on a smaller scale to understand what can be done to improve the outcomes of the main study and how (In, 2017). After the previous cohorts attempted to improve BG management at the pilot site without significant improvement, this QI project answered the why and gave insight on what should change to see considerable improvement in BG management.

The sample size for this QI project was established in agreement with the project lead and aimed for a 20% response rate from the barriers survey. This target, informed by the research of

Wu et al. (2022), suggests that in surveys with less than 500 participants, a 20%-25% response rate is generally adequate for obtaining representative responses. Achieving this rate in our project aligns with these guidelines and supports the reliability of the data collected. Thus, while a higher response rate might have been preferable, the 25% response rate achieved was in line with the recommendations of Wu et al. (2022) and sufficient for reaching thematic saturation, making the response rate a strength for this QI project.

Thematic saturation, a key critical juncture in qualitative research, was reached within the project's sample size ($n = 25$). Thematic saturation occurs when additional data collection yields no new information, allowing for the effective categorization and application of the data (Guest et al., 2020). This saturation was evident in the project, with recurring themes such as limited access to supplies and personnel-related issues emerging from the survey responses, as detailed in Appendix H.

The format of an online survey was a limitation of this QI project. While it has been found that response rates to online surveys have increased throughout the years, there is a greater response rate when there is an alternate form of completing the survey, for example, a paper survey, in addition to the online survey (Wu et al., 2022). The use of self-reported answers is an additional limitation. Self-reported responses tend to carry social desirability bias (Latkin et al., 2017). Social desirability bias is over-reporting information that wants to be heard and underreporting less desirable information. This bias can lead to skewed data findings (Latkin et al., 2017).

Qualitative studies, while helpful, are not the easiest to reproduce, making this a limitation for their general use to the public (Roberts et al., 2019). Quantitative studies typically have detailed explanations of their methods that make the reproduction of their study easier.

Since most qualitative studies have a vaguer description of their methods and the study conditions may be impossible to recreate, qualitative studies are low in reproducibility (Roberts et al., 2019). However, if the methodology of a qualitative study is well described and researchers find their sample population and circumstances similar, there is a high chance of reproducing the study.

An additional limitation was the limited time that did not allow for the full implementation of the EMR reminder tool. However, the barriers survey results provided insight into the causes of infrequent BG monitoring at the pilot site. As mentioned in the recommendations, cohorts taking over this project should employ the decision support tool and complete a chart audit following its implementation to supplement the findings from the survey and help resolve the issue of poor glycemic management at the pilot site.

Conclusion

The effects of poorly managed glycemic control in the perioperative setting for diabetic patients have been shown to result in adverse patient outcomes. This QI project aimed to increase adherence to intraoperative glucose monitoring and management among anesthesia providers at the pilot site. The survey results, themes, and insights are foundational data for developing interventions to improve perioperative glycemic management. Successful completion of this QI project has helped discover barriers and suggest possible interventions to improve the process of care that will ultimately improve BG management in patients with Type 2 DM receiving elective surgery.

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Appendix A

Barriers Survey

<p>1. What are potential barriers to appropriate perioperative hyperglycemic management? (Select all that apply)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a. Adequate access to supplies (e.g., glucometers, testing strips, rapid-acting insulin)b. Personnel (e.g., forgetting to check blood glucose)C. Lack of familiarity with the glycemic management protocol (Emory Protocol)
<p>2. Please elaborate on the answers in question one and/or note other barriers to care. (Free text answer)</p>
<p>3. What are some suggestions to improve perioperative glucose management? (Free text answer)</p>
<p>4. Would a reminder “pop-up” (clinical decision support tool) in HealthConnect be useful? (Yes or No answer)</p>

Appendix B

Audit Form

Field	Response	Explanation
Investigator		Number <i>E.g. 01</i> The unique number assigned to the primary investigator completing the form.
Surgery		Free text <i>E.g. Rotator cuff repair</i> The surgical proceed the patient is undergoing as listed on the operating list.
Length of surgery	hrs, min.	Free text <i>E.g. 2 hrs</i> From anesthesia start time to end of surgery.
Date of Surgery		DD/MM/YYYY <i>E.g. 10/10/2019</i> The date of the operation
ASA Grade	“ 1 “ 2 “ 3 “ 4 “ 5	Choose one The ASA of the patient as judged and documented by the anaesthetist anaesthetising the patient
Age	years	Numerical <i>E.g. 45</i> The age of the patient in years
Sex	“ M “ F	Choose one Male/Female
Weight	kg	Numerical <i>E.g. 87 kg</i> Patients weight as recorded pre-operatively
Height	ft., in.	Numerical <i>E.g. 5'8"</i> Patients height as recorded pre-operatively
Type of diabetes control	“ Diet “ Insulin “ Tablet “ Tablet & Insulin “ GLP1	Choose one The primary way the patient’s blood sugar is controlled in the community.
Pre-op HbA1c (within 3 months)	_____ % “ Not measured	Numerical/not measured <i>E.g. 6.5%</i>

Indicate the most recent HbA1c prior to surgical procedure date.

Diabetic medication	Frequency	Taken as usual	Alteration
		“ Y “ N	
		“ Y “ N	
		“ Y “ N	
		“ Y “ N	
		“ Y “ N	
<i>E.g. Metformin</i>	<i>E.g. OD</i>	<i>E.g. p N</i>	<i>E.g. Omitted</i>
List the patients usual anti-hyperglycaemic medication including tablets and insulins. Do not include secondary prevention medication	List the frequency the medication is taken	Choose one Was the medication taken as usual pre-operatively?	If the medication was not taken as usual, what was the change: Dose omission, dose alteration...
*Pre-anaesthesia BG	_____mg/dL “ Not measured		Numerical/Not measured <i>E.g. 115 mg/dL</i>
Anaesthesia start time			Time To closest 15 mins
Use of sliding-scale	“ Pre-op only “ Intra-op only	“ Pre & Intra op “ Not used (skip sliding-scale questions)	Choose one Was sliding-scale insulin used?
*Sliding-scale used appropriately per protocol	“ Yes “ No		Choose one Was insulin sliding-scale protocol followed?
*Sliding-scale insulin given within 30 minutes of BG results posting? (Exception: wait two hours after SQ dose before redosing SQ insulin)	“ Yes “ No		Choose one Was sliding-scale insulin given within 30 minutes?
Use of an insulin infusion	“ Pre-op only “ Intra-op only	“ Pre & Intra op “ Not used (skip insulin infusion questions)	Choose one Was an insulin infusion used?
If insulin infusion used, substrate given			Free text <i>E.g. Humulin R</i>

*Insulin infusion started and titrated appropriately per protocol	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Choose one Was insulin infusion protocol followed?
*Insulin infusion given within 30 minutes of BG results posting?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Choose one Was insulin infusion given within 30 minutes?
Use of IV/SQ insulin	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre-op only <input type="checkbox"/> Intra-op only	<input type="checkbox"/> Pre & Intra op <input type="checkbox"/> Not used Choose one Was IV/IM insulin administered?
If IV/SQ insulin used, substrate given		Free text <i>E.g. Humulin R</i>
If IV/SQ insulin used, dose and route given	_____ units <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> SQ	Numerical/Choose one <i>E.g. 2u IV</i>
Intraoperative BG	Highest _____ Lowest _____	Numerical range If only one taken write this number in the highest field
*Number of Intraoperative BG recordings and frequency	Number _____ Q2H Intra op: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Numerical
*D50 Protocol initiated and used appropriately	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not used	Choose one Was the D50 Protocol utilized appropriately?
Time entered recovery	:	Time To closest 15 mins
*BG in recovery	_____ mg/dL <input type="checkbox"/> Not measured	Numerical/Not measured <i>E.g. 180 mg/dL</i>
Patient discharged to:	<input type="checkbox"/> Home <input type="checkbox"/> Med/Surg <input type="checkbox"/> Telemetry <input type="checkbox"/> ICU	Choose one
Additional information		Free text If there is anything striking about this case which cannot be easily placed on the pro forma make a note of it here.

Note: *Asterisks show rows with regards to compliance to perioperative glucose protocol and measurements for the goals of this project.

Appendix C

Permission to use the Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare

 Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics Inbox - Exchange 12:56 AM
[External] Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care Hide
To: jdrellosa@csu.fullerton.edu,
Reply-To: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[Iowa Model - 2015.pdf](#)

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Reference: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:
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Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Appendix D

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare
 (2017). Used with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics

Figure 1

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare (2017).

Used with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics

Appendix E

Kaiser Permanente Non-Human Subjects Research Letter

InterOffice Memorandum

March 15, 2023

To: **Edward Waters, DNP, CRNA**
100 S. Los Robles Ave., Suite 501
Pasadena, CA 91188

Re: **Perioperative Glycemic Management of Patients Undergoing Elective Surgery**

Dear Dr. Waters,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l). Therefore, IRB review of this project is not necessary.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Armida Ayala".

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Appendix F

California State University Fullerton Institutional Review Board Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton

April 6, 2023

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Rachel McClanahan

Application No. HSR-22-23-343
Study Title: KPSA: Perioperative Glycemic Management of Patients Undergoing Elective Surgery

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording). Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office

Appendix G

Table 1: Data Evaluation and Measurement of Compliance with Perioperative Blood Glucose Protocol

Table 1

Evaluation and Measurement of Barriers and Compliance with Perioperative Blood Glucose Protocol

Outcome	Operational Definition	Method of Measurement	Analysis
Perceived barriers to perioperative blood glucose control	Information from survey on barriers	Barriers survey	Themes and patterns from compiled qualitative data
Suggested solutions to improve perioperative blood glucose control	Information from survey on solutions	Barriers survey	Themes and patterns from compiled qualitative data
Compliance with perioperative blood glucose control	Intraoperative documentation of BG value	Chart audits form	Percentage of provider compliance with BG checks according to protocol
	Insulin administration according to the protocol (SQ or IV)	Chart audits form	Percentage of provider compliance with intervention according to protocol
Hypoglycemia upon arrival to PACU	Number of patients who arrive at PACU	Chart audits form	Percentage of patients arriving in

	with hypoglycemia (BG <70 mg/dL)		PACU with hypoglycemia
Normoglycemia upon arrival to PACU	Number of patients who arrive at PACU with normoglycemia (BG 70 -130 mg/dL)	Chart audits form	Percentage of patients arriving in PACU with normoglycemia
Hyperglycemia upon arrival to PACU	Number of patients who arrive at PACU with hyperglycemia (BG >180 mg/dL)	Chart audits form	Percentage of patients arriving in PACU with hyperglycemia

Appendix H

Figures of Barriers Survey Results

Figure 2

What are Potential Barriers to Appropriate Perioperative Hyperglycemic Management (Select All That Apply)

Figure 3

Would a Reminder “Pop-up” (Clinical Decision Support Tool) in HealthConnect be Useful?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Would a reminder “pop-up” (clinical decision support tool) in HealthConnect be useful?	1.00	2.00	1.13	0.33	0.11	24

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	87.50% 21
2	No	12.50% 3

Figure 4

Free Text Responses to “What are Potential Barriers to Appropriate Perioperative Hyperglycemic Management?”

Figure 5

Free Text Responses to “What are Some Suggestions to Improve Perioperative Glucose Management?”

